

FROM THE EDITORS

This issue is devoted entirely to selected papers presented at the international conference on Small Area Estimation – SAE 2014. The conference took place at the Economics University of Poznan, from the 3rd to the 5th of September 2014. A satellite event – a workshop devoted to small area estimation with R given by Professor Li-Chun Zhang from the University of Southampton and Statistics Norway – was organized on the eve of the conference (September 2, 2014). The main aim of the SAE 2014 Conference was to provide a forum for the current research on small area estimation and related fields. The conference focused on aspects of conceptual, methodological and practical achievements in small area estimation methods in recent years. The conference brought together specialists from universities working on small area estimation, practitioners working in National Statistical Offices and other research agencies, all over the world. The SAE 2014 Conference was organized as part of activities of the European Working Group on Small Area Estimation and was the next in the series of conferences which have so far been held in Jyväskylä, Pisa, Elche and Trier.

The Programme Committee of the Conference was chaired by Professor Domingo Morales, Universidad Miguel Hernández de Elche. The Organizing Committee of the SAE 2014 Conference was chaired by Professor Marcin Szymkowiak, Poznan University of Economics. More details about these committees are available at this link: <http://www.sae2014.ue.poznan.pl/index.html>.

Statistics in Transition has previously published seven issues that focused on SAE, starting with articles from the Warsaw International Conference held in 1992 (*Vol. 1, Number 6, 1994*), and ending in 2005-6 with two issues (*Vol. 7, No. 3, December 2005*, and *Vol. 7, No. 4, March 2006*) with selected articles from The Conference held at the University of Jyväskylä, Finland, from 27-31 August 2005.

This time, in view of the large number of papers (15), the SAE 2014 proceedings were split into two parts: the first one appeared in December 2015. This is the second part of this thematic issue. These proceedings mark a turning as they were co-edited by Professor Włodzimierz Okrasa, Editor of *Statistics in Transition*, and Dr. Michael Hidiroglou, Editor of *Survey Methodology*. This joint editorship is a first between our journals, and it was a pleasure and memorable experience for both editors to collaborate.

These two issues represent a subset of the invited articles presented at the conference. They all went through a formal review process that was shared by four Guest Editors: Professor Risto Lehtonen (University of Helsinki), Finland,

Professor Ray Chambers (University of Wollongong), Australia, Dr. Graham Kalton (Westat), U.S.A., and Professor Malay Ghosh (University of Florida), U.S.A. Both editors, Professor Okrasa and Dr. Hidirolou, are very grateful for the excellent collaboration and efficient work of the Guest Editors. Our appreciation goes also to authors, especially those who had directly collaborated with us or with our editorial offices on adjusting their papers to our journals' technical requirements.

It is with great satisfaction that we, as editors, provide the reader with such a unique collection of papers representing not only the state-of-the-art variety of small area estimation topics, but also a great deal of thoughtful suggestion for exploration in further research.

Michael Hidirolou

Włodzimierz Okrasa

Editors